

حصول علم میں سوال و جواب کے کلچر کا کردار

ROLE OF QUESTION ANSWER CULTURE IN EDUCATION

Hafiz Haroon Riaz (ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6156-4502)

M.Phil. Research Scholar, Department of Usooluddin, University of Karachi.

Email: haronriaz@gmail.com, Cell: 03092148064, 03152508750

Tahira Firdous (ORCID ID: 0000-0002-1553-1133)

Assistant Professor, Faculty of Islamic Studies, University of Baluchistan, Quetta, Pakistan.

ABSTRACT

All greatness is for Allah, Durood and salaam for our master Prophet Muhammad ﷺ who is the seal of the Prophets. May Allah's mercy be on Prophet ﷺ companions and on those who travelled on their paths.

The reason why this topic was chosen is that the culture of questioning is gradually finishing, intentionally or unintentionally. The quantity of the people who ask and who answer, both have decreased, and nor do those who promote or support this culture have remained in the same quantity, whereas no one denies or questions the benefit of this culture. Only factor is some negligence and lack of attention, which often turns out to be a big loss, particularly when an individual questions their teacher with the intention of learning and understanding, they're eyed strangely as if he's made a wall fall.

Under the umbrella of this topic, I've tried to highlight the importance of the culture of questioning, primarily in the light of Quran, and secondly, in the light of Ahadith of the Prophet ﷺ, which shall enlighten the significance of this notion even further. Prophet Muhammad ﷺ, who was the greatest teacher of this ummah, after viewing and studying his life, we realize to what extent he utilized this culture in his students (companions of the Prophet ﷺ). And then, modern researches also let us know about the benefit this culture very rightfully so entails.

Keywords: Study, Education system, Islamic culture, Islamic institute.

کلیدی الفاظ: تعلیم، تعلیمی نظام، اسلامی تہذیب، اسلامی درس گاہیں۔

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7273332